

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENT SUBJECTIVITY IN THE PROCESS OF PREPARATION OF SPECIALISTS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

Yuldasheva Feruza Mamasakhatovna
Head of the Department of Preschool Education,
Termez State University

Annotation: The present is characterized by profound changes occurring in various areas of social life, including pedagogical science. They are caused by the globalization of socio-economic relations, the strengthening of the inamism of social processes, the all-encompassing information revolution, and, consequently, the strengthening of the importance of the individual in all manifestations of the life of a modern person. These changes require a revision of the target and content orientation of teaching activities and a radical restructuring of teacher education.

Keywords: pedagogy, students, competencies, innovative technologies, professional training.

Introduction. Despite the efforts of scientists, the active course of innovative processes in higher pedagogical education in the country, initiated by the Bologna process, in most higher educational institutions, unfortunately, the content and technologies of teacher training remain oriented towards the traditional knowledge and functional paradigm of education [2, 3, 5]. At the same time, in world pedagogical science and practice, a humanistic, personality-oriented model of education is increasingly being established, the priority goal of which is the holistic development of the individual, and not just the formation of him as a bearer of a certain body of knowledge [1, 5].

Let us note that the problem of personal, subjective orientation of pedagogical activity and the thinking of a professional teacher is not new, and has recently become increasingly acute and relevant [4, 6, 7]. At the same time, the analysis of

theoretical sources indicates significant disagreements in the interpretation by representatives of different scientific schools and concepts of the conceptual apparatus of personality-oriented education, and therefore, behind each of these interpretations there are different technologies of practical activity.

The closest to our understanding of the basic ideas of the personal paradigm of pedagogical education is the one in which the essence of pedagogical activity is not reduced only to the “transfer” of knowledge and skills to students, to the knowledgeable, purely educational function of education. By the way, this function today can be partially performed by technical information teaching aids [8, 9, 11]. According to the researchers, pedagogical actions themselves are “arming with values, attitudes, meanings, and not just information as such.” Consequently, “any actions of the teacher outside the context of this subjective value relationship, outside the orientation towards the essential human properties that should be formed in the child, that is, outside the context of the personality-formulating situation, cannot be qualified as pedagogical or non-pedagogical” [10, 12, 13].

But, unfortunately, a gnostic approach to professional training still prevails at universities, in which students deal not with the context of professional activity, but with academic subjects. That is, the main goal of training remains the formation of strong scientific and subject knowledge [14, 15]. Real professional activity is characterized by the diversity of contexts for the use of pedagogical information, the complex nature of pedagogical situations that require systematic use, which makes it impossible to directly transfer knowledge into practice and requires their rethinking and reflection.

The severity of the process of preparing for external procedural characteristics, that is, such traditional actions as setting a problem, selecting material, control and analytical operations, comparing children’s activities with program requirements leads to the fact that even a successful student, having technologically mastered these important professional actions, practice faces numerous personal problems that require identifying his subjective position. So, a

gap in the process of professional training becomes obvious, associated with the formation of professional consciousness in future teachers, the development of intuition, and the acquisition of readiness for pedagogical reflection [16].

Awareness of this fact led to the consistent work of scientists and teachers of the Faculty of Social Sciences of Termez University to create a strategy for training professionally competent specialists in preschool and primary education based on a personality-oriented paradigm [17, 18]. The article intends to present the main positions on this strategy. But, before outlining its essence, we consider it necessary to define the key theoretical positions underlying the concept of professional training of a competent specialist:

1) a competency-based approach to the process of professional training requires a holistic system vision in the design and implementation of innovative technology containing content, procedural and control and diagnostic elements.

The implementation of a technological model for training a professionally competent specialist in the educational process in combination with scientific activities will allow the graduate to achieve a high level of readiness for psychological and pedagogical activities;

2) the learning process is based on the principle of free creative education, which allows students, taking into account state, university requirements and development trends in the European educational space, to build their own learning path according to the chosen profile;

3) research activity is the content dominant of the educational process. Scientific research by the faculty's teaching staff is implemented in monographs, collective works, teaching aids, scientific student works and scientific and methodological literature used in the process of professional training;

4) deep assimilation of diverse knowledge from different areas of psychological and pedagogical science and the formation of professional skills on their basis becomes possible only under the condition of active creative learning. The predominance of

interactive teaching methods over explanatory and illustrative ones is the only sure way to optimize the process of professional training;

5) the process of professional training, built on the basis of a competency-based approach, is impossible without emphasizing the subject position of the student as a future specialist. It is the subjective position that becomes the internal core of professional development due to the generation of significant value meanings of future activity that form the student's professional pedagogical consciousness. In contrast to the dominant cognitive-technological aspect characteristic of the traditional system of professional training, we consider the priority direction to be the implementation of a personalized approach associated with the deployment of an individual trajectory of professional development in the following sequence:

Step 1 – the formation of value professional orientations, the search for one's own place in the future profession (at the stage of studying the course “Introduction to the Specialty”, the theoretical foundations of pedagogical activity);

Step 2 – laying the foundations of reflective thinking, focusing on the subject-subject interaction of the teacher and students in the future profession (at the stage of studying the disciplines of the psychological and pedagogical cycle);

Step 3 – development of pedagogical reflection, readiness to solve professional and pedagogical problems at a constructive level (through the use of two-level interactive technologies: design-problem seminars - at the stage of theoretical understanding of the problem and organizational-activity game - at the stage of practical modeling);

6) management of the quality of professional training is carried out through the creation of a monitoring system, which provides, first of all, for the abandonment of traditional assessment based on the criteria of knowledge, skills and abilities. Secondly, with the definition of conceptually relevant criteria for assessing the quality of professional training: the formation of reflective pedagogical thinking; the presence of a subject position (professional self-image); development of professional consciousness of future teachers;

7) therefore, knowledge, abilities and skills cease to be valuable guidelines in themselves, but are considered as a means of identifying professional competence;

8) at all levels of interaction between teachers and students, a necessary condition is the rejection of the traditional “superposition” of the teacher in favor of parity relationships among all participants in the educational process, which is impossible without students, first of all, understanding the essence of conceptual positions and ideas.

Conclusions. Conceptual constructs determine the dynamics of this development and allow us to identify key procedural blocks:

1. The context-oriented block (professional tasks) allows you to integrate acquired knowledge, primary algorithmic methods of activity, the foundations of reflexive thinking, ensuring readiness at the undergraduate level to solve basic-level professional problems; at the master's level - readiness to solve problems of a constructive level.

2. Orientation towards pan-European models of vocational education, which are characterized by a dominant research component, initiated a change in the role and place of research work in the educational process. This is reflected in the procedural model in that in the adjusted model the block of research activity penetrates into all aspects of professional training, and does not exist separately, which allows not only to increase the level of the educational process, but also to form the qualities of a future specialist as a researcher and contributes to the future of professional mobility of a graduate of a higher educational institution.

Consequently, the reorientation of teacher education towards the personal paradigm and the corresponding restructuring of the process of training professionally competent specialists, with the support of this process by the state and society, can play a key role in the renewal of society as a whole.

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